

The Study Of Interleukin-6 as New Potential inflammatory Biomarker In Cerebrovascular Stroke: A case control study

Abstract:

Background: Cerebrovascular stroke is globally recognized as a leading cause for mortality and seen more severe neurologic complications and Prognosis and precise prediction is very challenging, especially during acute phase of the disease. Interleukin -6 is not a factor only involved in the immune response, but with many critical roles in major physiological systems including the nervous system. Aim of present study was to measure serum level of Interleukin-6 and their role as inflammatory markers in cerebrovascular stroke.

Methods: Hundred subjects were enrolled in the present study out of 50 healthy age and sex matched individuals were taken as healthy controls and they have no any evidence of Cerebrovascular stroke as per clinical examination. Serum level of interleukin-6 was measured by using quantitative enzyme linked immune sorbent assay (ELISA). Statistical analysis was carried out by using the SYSTAT software package for window version 12. The student's t test was applied for the statistical analysis and the results were expressed in mean± Standard Deviation (Mean ±SD).

Result: In current study, mean values of interleukin 6 were significantly increased ($p < 0.01$) in patients with cerebrovascular stroke as compared with healthy controls.

ROC curve was plotted for interleukin-6 in diagnosing cerebrovascular stroke. Area under the ROC curve was 0.9607 Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value of interleukin-6 were 95.80%, 92.3%, 92% and 96% respectively for detection of cerebrovascular stroke.

Conclusion: Interleukin -6 contributes in the severity of ischemic strokes and may be useful in diagnosis and management of disease.

Keywords: *Cerebrovascular stroke, inflammatory markers, interleukin-6*

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Introduction:

Stroke is a clinical syndrome that consist of the rapid development of clinical signs of global or focal disruption of cerebral function that last more than 24 hrs. it is second leading cause of death globally and third leading cause in low income countries.¹ In fact it is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in major industrial countries. Approximately 20 million people each year are suffering from stroke.² Furthermore researchers assume a rise in the number of cases in the subsequent 10 years due to increased life expectancy.^{1,3}

India will face enormous socio-economic burden to meet the costs of rehabilitation of stroke victims. Because the population, it is now surviving through peak years (age 55-65years) of occurrence of stroke.³ The two major mechanisms causing brain damage in stroke are ischemia and hemorrhage. The effects of ischemia are fairly rapid because the brain does not store glucose, the chief energy substrate and is incapable of anaerobic metabolism. Intracerebral hemorrhage originates from deep penetrating vessels and causes injury to brain tissue by disrupting connecting pathways and causing localized pressure injury.⁴ Scientific evidences suggested that, inflammation play as key factor in the pathological response of stroke. The majority of inflammatory reactions to acute cerebral ischemia are mediated by cytokines.^{5,6} Interleukin 6 (IL-6) is an interleukin that acts as both a pro-inflammatory cytokine and an anti-inflammatory myokine. In humans, it is encoded by the *IL6* gene. Interleukin-6 is a cytokine not only involved in inflammation and infection responses but also in the regulation of metabolic, regenerative, and neural processes.⁷ Plasma level of interleukin-6 may be used in determining the extent of ischemic stroke.⁸

The diagnostic and management of cerebrovascular accident is limited by lack of rapid diagnostic assay for use in emergency setting. Thus, in view of above information and several risk of complication, it is extremely essential to study the various biomarkers in cerebrovascular accident. The initial aim of study was to measure the serum interleukin-6 levels in cerebrovascular accident. Furthermore, the remarkable intention of present research was to evaluate the clinical performance of interleukin-6 in early diagnosis of cerebrovascular accident and monitoring tool for early prediction of ischemic stroke.

Material and method:

Study design: The present diagnostic case-control study was conducted at department of Biochemistry with collaboration of department of medicine of DVVPF's Medical College Ahmednagar in one year.....

Ethical clearance and Sample size calculation:

In present study, ethical clearance was taken by institutional ethical committee.

(Pharmac/IEC/2015-8) All participants providing informed consent and utmost care was taken during experimental procedure according to the declaration of Helsinki 1975.

Present study is quantitative study thus the sample size calculated by using the following formula,

$$\text{Sample size } n = 4 * \sigma^2 / E^2$$

n= sample size,

σ =Standard deviation in population

E= Allowable error

Thus, total 100 subjects were enrolled in the present study. Out of this, Total 50 patients between age group 21 to 75 years admitted in the IPD wards of department of neurology and department of medicine were taken for the study. Data included history and clinical examination of the patients 50 healthy age and sex matched individuals were taken as healthy controls and they have no any evidence of Cerebrovascular stroke as per clinical examination.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

a) Inclusion criteria: Adult stroke (age > 21 years) and within 24 hours of admission.

b) Exclusion criteria: Patients with a history of intra-arterial thrombolytic, intra-venous thrombolytic, neurointerventional, anti-inflammatory and antibiotic therapies were excluded from present study. In addition patients with a history of ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes due to having new cases, brain trauma, inflammatory and infectious diseases were excluded.

Methodology:

Approximately 2 ml blood was collected by venipuncture from antecubital vein of the forearm of each subject in plain vacuumed evacuated tube (yucca diagnostic) under aseptic conditions within 24 hrs after admission. Blood samples were centrifuged within 1 hour for serum collection.

Method:

1) Serum interleukin -6

Serum interleukin-6 was measured with commercially available quantitative enzyme linked immune sorbent assay (ELISA) kit which contain an antibody specific for Human IL-6 coated on a 96-well plate. Standards and samples were pipetted into the wells and IL-6 present in a sample was bound to the wells by the immobilized antibody. The wells were washed and biotinylated anti-Human IL-6 antibody was added. After washing away unbound biotinylated antibody, HRP-conjugated streptavidin was pipetted to the wells. The wells were washed again, then TMB substrate solution was added to the wells and color developed in proportion to the amount of IL-6 bound. The Stop Solution changes the color from blue to yellow, and the intensity of the color was measured at 450 nm.⁹

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis was carried out by using the SYSTAT software package for window version 12. The student's t test was applied for the statistical analysis and the results were expressed in mean ± Standard Deviation (mean ± SD). p values p < 0.05 for all parameters was considered to be statistically significant.

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis and the area under the curve was performed for determination of diagnostic performance of serum interleukin-6 in the all patients included in the study. The optimum cutoff values for determination of serum interleukin-6, was selected from ROC analysis and it used to dichotomously classify positive or negative serum interleukin-6 and used for calculating of diagnostic sensitivity and specificity.

Result:

Table No.1 shown that mean values of baseline characteristics and biochemical parameter like serum interleukin-6. Mean values of interleukin 6 were significantly superior (p < 0.01) in patients with cerebrovascular stroke as compared to healthy controls.

Table No. 2 shows the diagnostic performance of interleukin-6 in cerebrovascular stroke. Cut off value of interleukin-6 was 43pg/ml and used for analysis of Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value. In present study, an ROC curves was plotted for interleukin-6 in diagnosing cerebrovascular stroke. Area under the ROC curve was 0.96. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value of interleukin-6 were 95.80%, 92.3%, 92% and 96% respectively for detection of cerebrovascular stroke.

Discussion:

Stroke is one of the leading cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide. Approximately 20 million people each year will suffer from stroke and of these 5 million will not survive. Developing countries account for 85% of global deaths from stroke. Stroke is also a leading cause of functional impairments, with 20% of survivors requiring institutional care after 3 months and 15% - 30% being permanently disabled. Stroke is a life-changing event that affects not only the person who may be disabled, but their family and caregivers. Utility analyses show that a major stroke is viewed by more an half of those at risk as being worse than death.¹¹

Interleukin-6 acts as both a pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokine. Interleukin-6 stimulates target cells via a membrane bound interleukin-6 receptor, which upon ligand binding associates with the signaling receptor protein gp130. It is secreted by T cells and macrophages to stimulate immune response to trauma, especially burns or other tissue damage leading to inflammation.⁷ Interleukin -6 is not a factor only involved in the immune response, but with many critical roles in major physiological systems including the nervous system. IL-6 is now known to participate in neurogenesis (influencing both neurons and glial cells), and in the response of mature neurons and glial cells in normal conditions and following a wide arrange of injury models.¹²

In present study, mean values of serum interleukin-6 were significantly superior ($p < 0.01$) in patients with Cerebrovascular stroke as compared to healthy controls. Our findings confirm and expand upon previous reports which have shown that higher level of interleukin-6.^{8,13}

Sheyda shaafi et al have shown that, plasma level of interleukin-6 in ischemic stroke was significantly enhanced. The study also suggested that plasma level of interleukin-6 is of value in determining the extent of ischemic stroke and associated with mid- term outcome and mortality rate of the stroke patients.⁸

Craig J Smith et al have demonstrated that, there is significant correlation between peak plasma Interlukin-6 in the first week of ischemic stroke with both brain infract volume and outcome at 3 months. Their study also proof that relationship between peripheral inflammatory markers and extent of tissue injury.¹⁴ Recently Marios K Georgakis et al have studied on interleukin -6 signaling and cardiovascular disease. According to their study, causal effect of interlukin-6 mostly seen on ischemic stroke particularly large artery and small vessel stroke as well as a range of cardiovascular phenotypes thus interleukin -6 receptor blockade might represent a vlid therapeutic target for lowering cardiovascular risk.¹⁵

Benjaman hotter et al have found that there was a significant association of IL-6 levels with NIHSS scores at admission of ischemic stroke patients, They also showed that IL-6 is an inflammatory marker of cerebral parenchymal damage independent of systemic infections.¹⁶

Conclusion:

According to present study, Serum level of IL-6 in Cerebrovascular stroke was significantly increased which may show that it contributes in the severity of ischemic strokes so IL-6 can be used as potential inflammatory markers for Cerebrovascular stroke and thus measurement of IL-6 might be useful in diagnosis and management of Cerebrovascular stroke.

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Table1: Baseline characteristics and biochemical changes of controls and Cerebrovascular stroke subjects.

Sr. No	Variable	Controls (n=50) Mean ± SD	Cerebrovascular Stroke (n=50) Mean ± SD
1	Age	49±12.5	57±11.3
2	Gender (Male)	29	33
3	Female	21	17
4	Pulse rate	70.35±1.92	83.72±16.48*
5	Diastolic blood pressure	75.63±4.23	84.42±18.33*
6	Systolic blood pressure	112±7.45	130.02±29.51*
7	Interleukin -6	19.10±12.21	51.34±14.60*

Values were expressed in mean with Standard Deviation (Mean±SD),

*p<0.01-- considered as highly significant,

Table 2:**Diagnostic performance of Interleukin-6 in cerebrovascular stroke**

Variable	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive predictive value	Negative Predictive value
Interleukin -6	95.80%	92.3%	92.0%	96%
95% of CI	84.5% to 99.2%	80.5% to 97.5 %	79.8% to 97.4%	85.1% to 99.3%

Figure no.1 Dignostic performance of interleukin-6 (ROC curve)

ROC Curve for $y = 0.03\ln(x) + 0.99$
Area under curve = 0.9607
